

INTERRELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND BUSINESS LEADERSHIP AND THE ROLE OF BUSINESS EDUCATION IN DEVELOPING EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE: A STUDY ON MANAGERIAL PERCEPTIONS

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Abstract

Leadership deals with human traits in a collaborative way with an intention to get the most effective results. This study aims at exploring the intertwining connections between emotional intelligence (EI) and successful leadership by setting forth to find answers to six research questions. Data for the research have been collected from both primary and secondary sources, with 100 business professionals from top management levels of organizations in Bangladesh participating in a survey consisting of thirteen Likert-scale questions and one open ended question. The study revealed that EI is strongly associated with successful leadership – as portrayed in the correlation test results, is sometimes valued more than IQ by employers, can be taught or learned and if integrated into formal business education curricula, can assist universities produce more well-rounded and effective leaders. In relation to EI's contribution to successful leadership and its influence on decision-making, correlation of EI with performance and productivity, contribution of EI to organizational success, and management of employee relationship are factors of crucial importance. This study also identified the fact that the higher the EI is the higher the likelihood of evolving as an experienced leader. The gravity of incorporating EI component in business curriculum is imperative in this regard. To incorporate EI in business curricula, content development along the lines of self-awareness, emotion management, motivation, empathy, and social skills is crucial. In future, organizations can base their measurement of leadership performance on the findings of the study, concentrating more on the EI skills of leaders and less on their technical knowledge.

Keywords : *Business Curriculum, Business Education, Emotional Intelligence (EI), IQ, Leadership, Successful Leadership.*

1. INTRODUCTION

For decades, the business world disregarded the roles of emotions, and hence the roles of emotional intelligence (EI), in performance and productivity; business education used to focus entirely on the development of quantitative skills and analytical knowledge. However, as proved by various studies (Ashkanasy, 2004), this scenario has changed and is still changing. The concept of EI started to gain scientific and corporate attention when Peter Salovey and Jack Mayer coined the term in 1990 and Daniel Goleman came up with his book “Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More than IQ” in 1995. Although, at the beginning, their ideas

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and theories provoked controversies among scientists and corporate leaders, due to emotions generally being considered an obstacle to rational thinking and quality performance, numerous studies in the subsequent periods proved that EI is directly related with high-performing, effective and successful leadership and is, in many ways, more important than IQ, technical skills or academic excellence.

Multiple studies and anecdotal reports in recent years have revealed that people with high EI are considered model employees as they possess the ability to handle different kinds of professional situations of varying natures with grace (Bryan, 2019). According to studies that depict the interrelationships between EI and leadership skills, individuals with high EI skills develop appropriate leadership behavioral skills highly sought and favored by colleagues, subordinates, top management and the organization as a whole. In general, hiring managers today are addressing more the need to employ individuals with high EI skills – employees who can resolve conflicts better, cope with high-pressure situations at work, cooperate with people from diverse backgrounds and make decisions in thoughtful manners (Bryan, 2019). At the same time, business degree is considered to be one of the most popular college degrees (Malvik, 2020). As a result, business schools are being asked more and more to incorporate EI into their curricula to produce better leaders for the job market. However, there are differing opinions regarding whether EI can be formally taught or learned. Some question the viability of formal EI education in terms of creating more successful leaders. This research, therefore, focuses on the intertwining connections between emotional intelligence, business education and successful leadership by setting forth to find answers to five research questions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Business Education: The Ever-changing Definition and the Early History

Business education, in the simplest terms, is defined by many as the courses that prepare individuals for the business world. However, the definition as well as the nature of business education is always evolving. According to Popham, Schrag and Blockhus (1975), when a group of people were asked the definition of business education, their responses were as diverse as from calling it an avenue to make enormous profit to economic concepts necessary for living in a business economy.

Popham's own version, based on different views of business educators, defined business education as a preparatory course for students before their entry into and advancements in jobs within business, for future entrepreneurs to manage their business affairs and for individuals to function wisely as consumers and citizens in a business economy. While in 1989, Osuala defined business education as a vital element of young people's preparations for life and living, in 2004 he explained it as a program of instructions carrying two parts – (1) Office Education which is a vocational program of office careers through education and (2) General Business Education which is a program to equip students with necessary information and competencies needed to manage personal business affairs and to use services provided by businesses.

The very first business education degrees were created in the US in the 1880s with the goal of formalizing education for future business leaders (Kelly, 2019). The Wharton Business School at the University of Pennsylvania and the Haas School of Business at the University of California, Berkeley started their journey into formal business education within a few years of each other. Now it’s the 21st century and business education is one of the most popular college degrees all over the world (Malvik, 2020), with 386,201 bachelor’s degrees for business majors having been conferred only in the US in the 2017-2018 academic year, according to the most recent data published by the National Center for Education Statistics (NCES).

2.2 Emotional Intelligence : Definition

Popular definitions of emotional intelligence (EI), also known as emotional quotient (EQ), refer to various things such as motivation, empathy, optimism, sociability and warmth. The term “emotional intelligence” was first coined by Mayer and Salovey in 1990 who defined it as a subset of social intelligence that enables humans to monitor emotions of their own as well as of others so that they can differentiate among them and use the resulting information to guide their thinking and actions. As per their definition, EI refers to *“the ability to perceive accurately, appraise, and express emotion; the ability to access and/or generate feelings when they facilitate thought; the ability to understand emotion and emotional knowledge; and the ability to regulate emotions to promote emotional and intellectual growth”* (Mayer & Salovey, 1997, p. 10).

In 1995, a large audience was, for the first time, familiarized with the term “emotional intelligence” by Daniel Goleman who defined EI as a group of five skills that enable leaders to maximize performances of their own and of their followers. In many of his studies, he (1995, 1998a, 1998b, 2000) elaborated its importance as a set of skills necessary to succeed in business and thus, popularized the idea of EI in the business world. Goleman’s five EI skills are as follows:

Source: Harvard Business School Publishing Corporation, 2003

Figure 1 : Modified Model of Daniel Goleman’s Five EI Skills

2.3 Leadership and Successful Leadership

Definitions of leadership have evolved over time, resulting in an exceptionally large array of perspectives, frameworks and concepts. Even the most prominent leadership scholars hardly agree on how leadership is or should be defined (Huber, 2002). Bernard Bass once famously wrote in this regard that “there are almost as many different definitions of leadership as there are persons who have attempted to define the concept” (Bass, 1990, p. 11). More interestingly, perhaps to elude disagreements, scholars often do not even define leadership. In his study of 587 scholarly works on leadership, Ross (1991) found that more than 60% works did not have the definition of the term even though it was the focus of the research.

Successful leadership is key to delivering power and intellect in leading an organization to the successful accomplishment of its goals. Not all leaders can transcend the title of “manager” or “boss”; those who do, do so by finding ways to achieve the right combination of charisma, enthusiasm and self-assurance. As per one definition, successful leadership refers to the kind of leadership that entails being able to self-manage, acting strategically, being an effective communicator, being accountable and responsible, setting clear goals and persisting in achieving them, having a vision for the future, managing complexity, fostering creativity and innovation, team building and promoting teamwork, creating lasting relationships and learning agility.

2.4 Emotional Intelligence as Part of the Business Education Curriculum

Since the term “emotional intelligence” was first coined by Mayer and Salovey in 1990, the concept of EI has been developed, adapted and embraced not only by the business world but also by numerous educators (Abraham, 2006). Several studies have found strong associations between EI skills and dynamic leadership (Goleman 1998a, 2000; Goleman, Boyatzis, & McKee, 2002) and several others have recognized the importance of EI for achieving success at the workplace (Goleman, 1998b). Abraham in her study (2006) emphasized the importance of EI as recognized by business, especially the accounting profession, and addressed the limitation of business education literature in this area.

Business environment in today’s world is increasingly demanding individuals with greater intrapersonal awareness and interpersonal communication skills. As a result, business schools all over the world are being asked by the industry to increase their focus on communication coursework in the business curriculum. In a report issued by the Management Education Task Force of the Association to Advance Collegiate Schools of Business (AACSB) in 2002, business schools were advised to increase their attention in communication, leadership and interpersonal skills in order to make their curriculum more relevant to today’s changing global workplace (Doria, Rozanski, & Cohen, 2003). As a response to suggestions from industries, alumni and executive advisors, many business schools around the world are now acknowledging that their students need to be taught soft skills that are essential in setting exemplary managers apart from their typical peers (Alsop, 2002).

2.5 How Emotional Intelligence Leads to Successful Leadership

Daniel Goleman, in his book “Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ” (1995), shared his insights, based on the results of various scientific studies conducted over a period of 20 years, as to why and how emotional intelligence can lead to highly successful leadership. Goleman argued that strong IQ or academic intelligence can build the foundation for success in life but in no way offers instructions on how to prepare for the turmoil or opportunities life’s vicissitudes bring to people’s lives. Later, his Harvard Business Review article “What Makes a Leader” (1998) emphasized on the importance of EI in successful leadership by citing multiple studies that favored the idea that it is EI, not IQ or academic excellence, that distinguishes a great leader from an average leader.

While initially Goleman’s ideas and theories raised a lot of eyebrows in corporate circles, they caught the attention of the senior management at Johnson & Johnson’s Consumer Companies (JJCC), a company long committed to leadership education and development. JJCC then took on a study, by involving more than fourteen hundred employees in thirty-seven countries, to assess the role of emotional, social and relational competencies, identified by Goleman and other EI theorists, in distinguishing high performing leaders across the company (Cavallo & Brienza, 2006). The study found a strong relationship between high performing leaders and EI; leaders who received performance ratings of 4.1 or more on a 5-point scale were rated considerably higher than other participants in all the four dimensions of EI – self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and social skills – by their supervisors and subordinates.

According to some researchers, EI is positively linked to transformational style of leadership (Barling, Slater, & Kelloway, 2000), which is one type of leadership that involves creating a vision, communicating this vision, building commitment amongst subordinates to the vision and modeling the vision within the workplace. Barling, Slater and Kelloway (2000), in their exploratory study on the relationship between EI and transformational leadership, demonstrated that EI has a strong association with three aspects of transformational leadership - idealized influence, inspirational motivation and individualized consideration – and leaders exhibiting these behaviors are assumed to be more effective at the workplace.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

While some studies set forward to determine the relationships between emotional intelligence and successful leadership and some others to identify the needs for the integration of EI in business education curriculum, few have endeavored to incorporate emotional intelligence, business education and successful leadership in one single study. The objective of this research, therefore, is to explore the connections between emotional intelligence, business education and successful leadership by answering the following questions.

Table 1 : Six Research Questions of the Study

Research Question 1	Does emotional intelligence (EI) contribute to successful leadership? If yes, how?
Research Question 2	Is EQ/EI more important than IQ in creating successful leaders?
Research Question 3	Can EI be taught or learned?
Research Question 4	Can business education, when EI is integrated into it, be more effective in creating successful leaders?
Research Question 5	Should business education curriculum have specialized modules dedicated to the teaching of EI?
Research Question 6	What is the strength of the relationship between EI and Leadership?

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In researching the interconnections between emotional intelligence, business education and successful leadership, qualitative and quantitative data have been collected from both primary sources and secondary sources.

Data Collection Sources

Table 2 : Primary and Secondary Data Sources

Primary Sources	To collect data from primary sources, a survey questionnaire was prepared with thirteen Likert-scale questions on the research topic that asked the respondents to strongly disagree, disagree, be neutral, agree or strongly agree to the statements and one open ended question that asked the respondents to share their opinions on the research subject. The questionnaire was shared in an online business platform and purposive sampling was used to collect responses from 100 business executives in Bangladesh who participated in the survey. The respondents were chosen based on judgement sampling method; at the start of the questionnaire, a question was asked to find out whether the respondent had heard the term EI before and had basic knowledge of the terminology. Those who chose yes were taken to the main part of the questionnaire; those who did not, were not taken to the subsequent parts.
	Two business leaders in Bangladesh were approached and through an in depth interview they opined their views on the research topic. Purposive sampling method was used in this process; this sampling process was used to ensure that the purpose of gaining in-depth knowledge with regards to the EI is served. Both the chosen leaders had obtained corporate training on EI.

Secondary Sources	While collecting secondary data, the researchers conducted exhaustive reviews of many digitally available national and international academic articles, journal articles and newspaper and magazine articles that explored this area of research.
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Data Analysis Methods

The survey data was used for both descriptive and inferential statistics. As part of descriptive statistics, the Likert scale responses were summarized to find out what percentage of the respondents perceived a strong relationship between EI and leadership. Other responses in this regard were also analyzed. Second, with regards to inferential statistics, correlation tests and independent samples t-test were run using the collected data to check the interrelationship among the variables of interest of this study. Finally, the collected qualitative data was analyzed using template analysis technique to find out major themes mentioned in the interview accounts.

5. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

5.1 Does Emotional Intelligence (EI) Contribute to Successful Leadership?

Before finding whether EI positively impacts successful leadership and if it does, how, this research intended to find whether business executives think there is a relation between emotions and performance and productivity. In this regard, responses were collected from 100 respondents in a survey format. For analysis of the results, responses to the following statements were dissected first: ‘Human emotions are strongly correlated with performance and productivity’, ‘Leaders with high EI can make greater contributions to organizational success than leaders with low EI’, ‘EI helps leaders improve their decision-making’, ‘EI helps build great teamwork within an organization’, ‘EI helps leaders effectively manage their relationships with the employees’, ‘EI helps leaders adapt better to changes’.

For analysis purposes, first, Likert scale responses were counted for each of these statements and a weighted scoring system was developed for each of these statements. To illustrate, 18 people responded strongly disagree, 4 responded disagree, 6 responded neutral, 23 responded agree, and 49 responded strongly agree to the first statement. Then, to find out the relative importance given to this statement/factor, each rating on the Likert scale (1, 2, 3, 4, 5) was multiplied by the respective number of respondents. So, the score obtained by the first statement is = $1 \times 18 + 2 \times 4 + 3 \times 6 + 4 \times 23 + 5 \times 49 = 245$. The following graph shows the scores obtained by each of these statements:

Figure 2 : Influence of EI on Decision Making

As it can be seen from the chart above, the mean score of all the six questions is 370.5. Furthermore, the scores reveal that factors related to correlation of EI with performance and productivity, contribution of EI to organizational success, and management of employee relationship are perceived to be more important as they scored higher than the average. On the other hand, factors related to decision-making, teamwork, and adaptability to change are perceived to be less important. Thus, in relation to EI’s contribution to successful leadership and its influence on decision-making, correlation of EI with performance and productivity, contribution of EI to organizational success, and management of employee relationship are factors of crucial importance.

In addition to the above findings, the next Likert-scale question on the survey probed to find what people think about EI and its effects on successful leadership. Results of this question, as has been graphically presented below, revealed that an impressively large portion of people (70%) believe EI/EQ is key to successful leadership, with 34% strongly agreeing and 36% agreeing to the statement. The rest of the respondents (30%) seem to think that other factors like IQ, academic intelligence or hard skills, not EI, are key to leadership success.

Source : Adapted from the online survey

Figure 3 : Survey Responses to Whether Emotional Intelligence (EI)/Emotional Quotient (EQ) Is Key to Successful Leadership

These results signify that there has been a growing recognition of EI, in the business world, as an important factor behind successful leadership over the last few decades. As per studies, in today's highly dynamic business environment, technical skills may help graduates secure a job but eventually it's their EI skills that will decide how far they will move on the company leadership. EI is what helps leaders successfully coach teams, manage stress, deliver feedback and collaborate with others and as per Goleman (1998a, 2004), accounts for nearly 90% of what sets high performers apart from their peers with the same technical skills and knowledge. This resonates with Goleman's (2004) findings where he noted an outperformance of yearly targets by up to 20% by the division in which the employees had higher EI capacities.

5.2 Is EQ/EI More Important than IQ in Creating Successful Leaders?

Goleman's general hypothesis (1995, 1998a, 2004) that EQ is better than IQ in indicating professional success and his initial research methods in proving the hypothesis garnered criticism from both the scientific community and the corporate world (Bryan, 2019); however, his subsequent studies supported his initial theories – in a study of skills that distinguish high performers at every level of organizations, Goleman found that the most important factor was EQ/EI, not IQ, advanced degrees or technical experience, with EQ being 67% of the competencies required for excellence in performance. In a 2011 survey, involving 2,600 hiring managers, conducted by CareerBuilder, 71% said that they valued EQ over IQ and 75% said they were more likely to promote employees with high EQ scores (Bryan, 2019). In explaining their viewpoints, those managers said, in order of importance, that employees with high EQ – (i) are more likely to stay calm under pressure, (ii) know how to effectively resolve conflicts, (iii) feel empathy towards their team members and react accordingly, (iv) lead by example and (v) tend to make more thoughtful business decisions (CareerBuilder, 2011).

Source : Adapted from the online survey

Figure 4 : Survey Responses – Whether High EQ is More Important in Creating Successful Leaders than High IQ

The results of the survey created for this research showed that a large percentage of people are not sure about whether high EQ, not high IQ, is more important for

successful leadership. While 8% respondents strongly disagreed and 18% disagreed to the statement, 27% remained neutral. However, 30% respondents agreed and 17% strongly agreed to the statement, so the number of people who actually believe that EQ is more important than IQ is not much low.

5.3 Can EI be Taught or Learned?

One of the most controversial aspects of EI is whether or not it can be taught or learned. Goleman in his article “What Makes a Leader?” (1998a, 2004) argued that much like leadership, EI can be taught and learned even though learning EI is much harder than learning the regression analysis. The survey of this research had two Likert-scale questions about whether EI can be taught or learned, the responses of which are presented in the following chart.

Source : Adapted from the online survey

Figure 5 : Survey Responses to Whether EQ Can be Taught or Learned

The two statements – (i) EI can be taught and (ii) EI can be learned – received mixed responses from the respondents. 27% respondents remained neutral to the idea that EI can be taught and 23% to the idea that EI can be learned; these percentages show that many people, especially in countries like Bangladesh where EI skills have not been integrated into formal business education and performances are almost always measured on the basis of numbers, are not convinced that EI can be formally taught or learned. While a total of 29% respondents disagreed that EI can be taught and a total of 31% that EI can be learned, a total of 44% and 46% respondents agreed to the statements respectively. Thus, it can be said that the findings in this section does not completely agree with the findings of Goleman’s article (1998a, 2004) mentioned above. In his article, he argued that even though people are born with certain levels of EI, through proper practice, perseverance, guidance, and feedback, EI can be developed among employees. All the five components of EI as illustrated by him in that article namely self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, social skill, can be groomed in the managers.

5.4 Can Business Education, When EI is Integrated into It, be More Effective in Creating Successful Leaders?

According to some studies (Elliot, Goodwin, & Goodwin, 1994), many employers believe that formal business education like MBA programs excessively focus on quantitative skills and analytical abilities and disregard the development of qualitative management and people skills. Business curricula that produce graduates with high EI skills are, therefore, being recognized and rewarded by recruiters, with EI being a better metric than academic quality and research expertise (Alsop, 2002). So, it can be argued that EI education as part of formal business curriculum can highly contribute to producing future leaders with great EI.

Table 3 : Survey Responses to the Two Questions Concerned with the Incorporation of EI in Formal Business Education

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Formal business education can be more effective in creating successful leaders when EI is integrated into it.	14%	10%	17%	40%	19%
EI, when taught to business students, can help them explore their own self-awareness and interpersonal awareness that can lead to behavioral changes essential for successful leadership.	18%	5%	11%	44%	22%

Source : Adapted from the online survey

Survey responses to the above two statements show that even though a large group of people are either against or neutral to the idea that EI can be taught (56%) or learned (54%), many of them, along with others, believe that (i) if EI is taught as part of formal business education, the curriculum can be more effective in creating successful leaders (a total of 59% respondents - 19% strongly agreeing and 40% agreeing) and (ii) when EI is taught to business students, they have better self-awareness and interpersonal awareness, leading to successful leadership (a total of 66% respondents – 22% strongly agreeing and 44% agreeing). Thus, in line with the previous study findings mentioned earlier (Alsop, 2002), it can be said that majority of the respondents in this study agree with the importance of EI inclusion in the business curricula in preparing effective leaders. As mentioned by Alsop, rather than including finance, marketing, or management knowledge in the curriculum, leadership, communication skill, and team adaptability- these three skills should be incorporated in the curriculum as they are sought after by recruiters for leadership positions.

5.5 Should Business Education Curriculum Have Specialized Modules Dedicated to the Teaching of EI?

To adapt better, survive and/or excel in today’s changing market, organizations are increasingly addressing the need to hire graduates who have good communication skills, foster relationships, have purposes, establish loyalty and commit to their responsibilities. Employers now need college graduates who know how to think, how to learn and how to communicate. Following data from the National Association of Colleges and Employers (NACE) show some of the EI skills and qualities – beyond a sound GPA and technical knowledge – that employers most want to see on resumes (NACE, 2018) –

Table 4 : Attributes Employers Seek on a Candidate’s Resume

Skills and Qualities	% of Respondents
Communication Skills (Written)	82.0%
Ability to Work in a Team	78.7%
Communication Skills (Verbal)	67.4%
Leadership Skills	67.4%

Source : Adapted from Job Outlook 2019, National Association of Colleges and Employers

Therefore, “To better meet the demands and challenges of today’s public education system, research studies indicate that the development of emotional skills should be in the academic curriculum to produce healthy, responsible, and productive students” (Vela, 2003, p. 1-2).

Adapted from the online survey

Figure 6 : Survey Responses to Whether Business Education Curriculum Should Have Specialized Modules Dedicated to the Teaching of EI

This particular statement that business curriculum should have specialized modules to teach students EI derived interesting responses from the survey respondents of this research. While a significantly large portion of people strongly disagreed, disagreed or remained neutral to the ideas that EI can be taught (56%) or learned (54%), a hefty total of 65% respondents agreed that EI skills should be integrated as specialized

modules into formal business education curriculum. The rest 35% of the respondents, not as certain about the effectiveness of the formal teaching of EI as the others, strongly disagreed (16%), disagreed (7%) or remained neutral (12%) to the idea.

5.6 Relationship between EI and Leadership

The Likert scale data were used to statistically analyze the relationship between EI and leadership.

For each of the following correlation tests below, responses from 1-6 for the Likert scale questions were used as input in SPSS. For example, in the first test, responses to “Emotional intelligence (EI)/Emotional quotient (EQ) is key to successful leadership” and “Leaders with high EI can make greater contributions to organizational success than leaders with low EI” were used as inputs. The relevant variables here are EI and leadership. Now, after running the correlation test, if the result indicates strong positive relationship, it indicates that those who believe that EI is key to successful leadership also believes that EI makes greater contribution to organizational success. So, the high correlation ensures that the perceptions held by the respondents regarding EI and leadership are not arbitrary, rather it is consistent. It would have been inconsistent if the correlation values were negative. So, through all these correlation tests below, the researcher will analyze the consistency and strength of perceptions held by the respondents about EI and leadership.

As described above, responses to these questions were used for the first correlation test: “Emotional intelligence (EI)/Emotional quotient (EQ) is key to successful leadership” and “Leaders with high EI can make greater contributions to organizational success than leaders with low EI”. As measures of the components of this test, ordinal scale data was used from the Likert scale responses. To elaborate, all the ordinal scale responses to the first question was correlated against all the ordinal scale responses to the second question. To mention here, the same principle applies to the subsequent correlation tests.

Table 5 : Correlation Test between EQ and Successful Leadership

Correlations			
		EQ	Leadership and Organizational Success
EQ	Person Correlation	1	.730
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Leadership and Organizational Success	Person Correlation	.730	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

In the table above, “EQ” stands as the short form representation of emotional quotient and represents the ordinal scale responses to the first question; on the other hand, “leadership and organizational success” represents the ordinal scale responses to the second question.

As shown in the table above, the correlation value is 0.73, indicating strong positive relationship. This value indicates that those who perceive that EI/EQ is key to successful leadership also perceive that leaders with high EI can lead to greater organizational success, thus denoting a strong relationship in each respondent’s perception of EI (from first question), leadership and organizational success (from second question). The significance value is less than 5% for this test, indicating that the test result is significant.

In the next test, correlation was run between the responses from these two questions: “High EQ is more important in creating successful leaders than high IQ” and “Emotional intelligence can be taught”.

Table 6 : Correlation Test between EI and Teaching of EI

Correlations			
		EI	Teaching
EI	Person Correlation	1	.680
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Teaching	Person Correlation	.680	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

In the table above, “EI” stands as the short form representation of emotional intelligence and represents the ordinal scale responses to the first question; on the other hand, “teaching” represents the ordinal scale responses to the second question.

As shown in the table above, the correlation value is 0.68, indicating moderate positive relationship. This value indicates that those who perceive that EI is important in developing leadership also perceive that EI can be taught rather than believing that EI is something achieved at birth, thus denoting a moderate relationship in each respondent’s perception of EI and the teaching of EI. The significance value is less than 5% for this test, indicating that the test result is significant.

This relationship was also observed in the correlation test result between the responses to “High EQ is more important in creating successful leaders than high IQ” and “Emotional intelligence can be learned and mastered with formal coaching and practice”. In the table below, “EI” stands as the short form representation of emotional intelligence and represents the ordinal scale responses to the first question; on the other hand, “coaching” represents the ordinal scale responses to the second question.

As shown in the figure below, the correlation value is 0.76, indicating strong positive relationship. This value indicates that those who perceive that EI is important in developing leadership (from first question in this test) also perceive that EI can be developed through coaching (from second question in this test), thus denoting a strong relationship in each respondent’s perception of EI and the coaching of EI. The significance value is less than 5% for this test, indicating that the test result is significant.

Table 7 : Correlation Test between EI and Coaching of EI

Correlations			
		EI	Coaching
EI	Person Correlation	1	.760
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Coaching	Person Correlation	.760	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

Finally, in the quest for relationship between EI and leadership, one last correlation test was run between the responses to “High EQ is more important in creating successful leaders than high IQ” and “EI helps leaders adapt better to changes”.

Table 8 : Correlation Test between EI and Agility of Leaders

Correlations			
		EI	Leadership and Agility
EI	Person Correlation	1	.710
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Leadership and Agility	Person Correlation	.710	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

In the table above, “EI” stands as the short form representation of emotional intelligence and represents the ordinal scale responses to the first question mentioned earlier; on the other hand, “leadership and agility” represents the ordinal scale responses to the second question mentioned above.

As shown in the table above, the correlation value is 0.71, indicating strong positive relationship. This value indicates that those who believe in EI’s importance (from the first question in this test) also perceive that leaders are better at accommodating with changes (from the second question in this test), thus denoting a strong relationship in

each respondent’s perception of EI, leadership and agility – a crucial characteristic of leaders. The significance value is less than 5% for this test, indicating that the test result is significant. To summarize the above test results, all the inferential analysis above indicates a strong positive relationship between the perceptions held about EI and leadership.

To further understand the relationship between EI and leadership, t-test was also done to see whether the rating with regards to the importance of leadership and EI varies. For this purpose, response to the following two questions were used: “Emotional intelligence (EI)/Emotional quotient (EQ) is key to successful leadership” and “Leaders with high EI can make greater contributions to organizational success than leaders with low EI”.

Table 9 : Mean Difference between the Perception of EI and Leadership

Group Statistics					
	L1	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
L3	1.00 Question 1	100	4.3684	.99786	.16187
	2.00 Question 2	100	4.5100	1.17842	.14966

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene’s Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
L3	Equal variances assumed	3.678	.058	-1.066	98	.289	-.14160	.22945	-.69981	.21085
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.109	88.199	.270	-.14160	.22046	-.68258	.19362

As the table above shows, the mean score of the responses to these questions are very close. Based on the significance test value, we can say that there is no statistically significant difference between the scores given to the importance of EI and leadership, thus again proving the relationship between these two variables; the significance level of the test results also supports the findings of no significant difference.

5.7 The Business Leaders’ Thought

Five business leaders were approached for this study and two of them responded. The MD and CEO of a leading telecommunication operator said that “a leader with emotional intelligence impacts various aspect of self and factors around us which includes – self-awareness, self-confidence, self-development, engagement with employee and stakeholders, self and team motivation, team performance, environment of trust, driving innovating and creative behavior etc. In the digital

era where transformational changes are rapid and fast, the need of EI among leaders are far more required than ever before....As a leader you set the tone for the kind of collaboration that takes place in the organization. It starts with making people comfortable in your presence. If the leader has high level of EI, he/ she will demonstrate a high degree of empathy to people..... But most importantly, I think EI-led leadership creates an environment where people feel safe to make mistakes. It also helps the leader to enthuse his/ her people to embrace a culture of life-long learning. At the end, I think EI is not something that a leader can try to be too conscious about or afford to be inconsistent about; it has to come from within. Hence, one can't fake it. So, anyone who wants to be an effective leader has to have a high level of EI and has to go through a life-long journey of introspection to get it right on most occasions”.

Another top management member of a multinational manufacturing company said, *“emotional Intelligence is a key for smart “self-growth”. In my view a leader will be handicapped if he/she does not embrace the value and application of emotional intelligence at work. EI allows the leaders to influence ideas and rally people behind the idea and grow”.*

The industry leaders strongly suggested that emotional intelligence is essential for any leader to help the employees as well as the company grow. They also stressed on the fact that the formal business education should incorporate the components which can increase the chance of nurturing emotional intelligence.

Another major contribution of these interview accounts was the design and content of the EI integrated business curricula. According to majority of the interview accounts, the incorporation of EI should be done as early as in the first or second year of undergraduate studies; there has to be a separate course on EI. Moreover, in other courses as well, the concept of EI has to be ingrained in such a way that learners can successfully interpret others' emotions, manage their own, and communicate empathy when dealing with others.

With regards to the core content of EI, the following 5 dimensions were mentioned by many: self-awareness, management of emotions, motivation, social skills, and empathy. Besides these qualitative aspects, quantitative measurement of people's EQ needs to be taught as well. With regards to the core dimensions, further details were also provided: in the discussion of self-awareness, core concept and understanding of the terminology, awareness of the surroundings, and setting one's own life positions with a self-aware mindset needs to be covered. With heightened level of self-awareness, one can control one's emotions. With regards to the dimension of emotion management, the scientific discussion of emotion, self-control, relaxation techniques, and coping mechanism with positive and negative emotions can be taught. Covering these topics in detail might help the students in managing their emotions better. Moreover, with regards to self-motivation, the concept of optimism and pessimism, the balance between the two, and the concept of reframing optimistic and pessimistic traits can be covered which might help an individual to master the concept of self-

motivation. Moving on, the discussion on empathy can focus on the development process of empathy in an individual. As it is an abstract process, in-class role-playing activities can be used here. Finally, with regards to social skills, the concept of social skills, first impression, assessment of a given situation, and development of the traits of a person with high social skills can be discussed. As part of this discussion, verbal communication skills (focused listening and orating) and nonverbal skills (signals, body language) can be practiced through situation-based learning activities (i.e., role playing). Designing the curricula along the abovementioned dimensions might promote an active incorporation of EI in business education.

The above interview accounts reveal some new elements of EI to be added besides those already proposed by Goleman. First, the interviewees suggested the addition of quantitative measures of EI in the curriculum so that individual's level of EI and improvement in EI can be calculated to find out the success of a curriculum. Moreover, while the interviewees mentioned self-awareness, motivation, social skills, and empathy that were also mentioned by Goleman, a new focus was suggested in the area of management of emotions under which the scientific discussion of emotion, self-control, relaxation techniques, and coping mechanism with positive and negative emotions were mentioned to be included in the curriculum. Finally, with regards to social skills which was also suggested by Goleman, the interviewees discussed specific aspects of social skills which are verbal communication skills (focused listening and orating) and nonverbal skills (signals, body language). These skills was suggested to be developed through situation-based learning activities (i.e., role playing).

6. CONCLUSION

While a certain group of population still believes that there are no strong associations between EI and successful leadership and business education do not need to integrate EI into their curriculum to produce better leaders, findings from various past and current studies point to entirely different scenarios in today's business world. It has been well established by these studies that leaders with high EI skills are better and more successful than leaders with low EI skills and therefore, are demanded more by employers and organizations. These studies have also showed that it has become increasingly important for students, especially business students, to graduate with well-honed levels of EI for better career success and fulfillment. Therefore, for business educators it is imperative to translate academic theories and research into practical applications in their programs and provide their graduates with strong foundations in EI training so that they become well-rounded individuals, worthy employees, effective managers and successful leaders.

Although this research succeeded in finding the interrelations between emotional intelligence, business education and successful leadership, it had some limitations that need to be addressed in future studies. It will be interesting to have further studies linking EI, business education and effective leadership in larger samples and across different industries, especially from the perspective of Bangladesh.

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